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PSO BASED OUT-OF-ORDER (OOO) EXECUTION SCHEME FOR HT-MPSOC

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, the influence of the dynamic task scheduling process is examined. Out-of-Order (OoO) implementation processes exhibit remarkable guarantee for task-level parallelism in multiprocessor system-on-chip (MPSoC) designs. The superior performance can be attained with the help of a precise mapping of tasks onto the right processors. Hence, to obtain this performance, a Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) based task parallelism is presented in this paper. The software related dynamic operations are illustrated on a heterogeneous MPSoC (Ht-MPSoC). PSO abides by a cooperative population-based search, which demonstrates upon the social activities of bird grouping. PSO system merges local search approaches with global search approaches. This implementation decreases the issue of task management. The performance of the proposed design is compared with the existing work for area, power and speed analysis.

Keywords: Multiprocessor System-on-Chip, Particle Swarm Optimization, task-level parallelism, Out-of-Order implementation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Heterogeneous computing modules provide improved performance at moderately low energy expenses. The presence of processing modules with distinctive features, computation process can be schemed to the specified elements that accomplish a certain kind of job more powerfully than other modules. Heterogeneous devices have one or many multi-core general-purpose CPUs and one or many throughput-oriented many-core processors. Extensive researches have been performed in this field due to many data-parallel applications and the necessity for superior performance. The most uncomplicated and modern topology that is promoted very quickly is the organization of the many-core processors on an add-on

dispensation that is attached to the module by means of a non-coherent interlock. This has two consequences. The CPU processing and its storage sub module are completely separated from the many-core processor (Graphic Processing Unit (GPU)) and its memory subunit, *i.e.*, the two memory subunits are not comprehensible and there is no collective memory. Hence the programming turns out to be problematic as the programmer must handle the data that is influenced by the CPU and the GPU. Then with the recent Peripheral Component Interconnect-Express (PCI-E) bandwidths, large data transfers between the two dispensation sub-units can devastate any speedup accomplished by the many-core once the processing is deliberated [1]. Those “loosely-attached” dispersed memory heterogeneous modules do not offer the engineer with an integrated assessment of the storage and compute units. The applications involving the acceleration from heterogeneous elements must be judiciously reported to notice data-parallel segments that could proceed from a many-core GPU. If GPU conventional operations are existing for the kernels, the programmer must obviously perform the kernel computations along with the mandatory data transfers.

Disseminated computing modules have developed as a prevailing place for stipulating advanced computational power necessitated by an extensive range of solicitations. The execution of a parallel operation on distributed scheme depends vastly on the application and the platform attributes. The application attributes are the implementation cost and communication overhead between tasks and the platform attributes are execution ability of the processors, number of processors, transmission bandwidth, storage, etc [2]. To meritoriously manipulate the dispersed elements, a significant problem is the representation of functions to processors with the purpose of attaining a certain objective, for example load balancing, reduction of interprocessor transmission or some combination of the two for computationally challenging tasks with miscellaneous computing requirements. The prevalent application of disseminated computers in numerous computationally rigorous functions makes the drawback of recording programs for distributed computers more essential.

Reconfigurable computing process is able to combine multifaceted application-exclusive computing features on a single chip. It is prophesied that Multiprocessor Systems on-Chip (MPSoCs) will momentarily develop computational competencies of heterogeneous platforms. Heterogeneous MPSoCs merge numerous modules like microprocessors, digital signal processors (DSPs), or intellectual property (IP) cores/accelerators, in a prefabricated manner. This offers a higher level abstraction for system engineers. MPSoCs becomes

heterogeneous since they merge several well-organized processing modules for a particular job. Conversely, reconfigurable computing introduces complexity to MPSoC by attaching the facility to acclimate the task of these modules through static or dynamic reconfigurability. This is also the vital factor for their less usage.

The implementation of multiple Out-of-Order (OoO) actions contains momentous problems to organize them and represent them on the computing units. At this stage, the major shortcoming of present programming systems is that program writers must regulate the assignments materially. It becomes a great trouble for them. The OoO execution is based on the scoreboarding and the Tomasulo algorithm [3] at the instruction level. These approaches deliver systems for OoO instruction implementation when there are enough computational provisions and no data threats among instructions. The Tomasulo protocol is more intricate because it is able to identify, write-after-write (WAW) and write-after-read (WAR) threats through register rechristening. Accordingly, as programming units need more experience from the researchers, the enlargement from the instruction-level scheduling process to task level process affords a different procedure to exploit MPSoC platform effectually. In this paper, we extend the instruction-level scoreboarding system to the task level. The motivations for using the scoreboarding are given below.

- 1) Scoreboarding stipulates a light-weight task threat apparatus for OoO accomplishment. The design is unpretentious, which produces lesser scheduling overheads.
- 2) For task-level parallelization, WAW and WAR threats do not transpire considerably at the instruction level. Many engineers plan to employ diverse measures to WAR and WAW hazards. Hence, the complex Tomasulo algorithm is not used.

Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm employs a collaborative population-based search pattern [4]. Every specific member of the population is known as particle. The particle hovers over a multidimensional search area and finds out the maximal solution. Particles may alter their locus in relation to their individual and adjacent-particles knowledge. Thus, they transfer in the direction of their optimal point or the optimal point of their adjacent particle. A particle retains the formerly attained optimal points in a perceptive memory, so that the movement to the optimal point can be attained. The function of PSO is observed in relative to a prefixed fitness function. Stabilizing between global and local investigation facilities of the hovering particles could be realized over user-defined measures.

PSO has many benefits when compared with other heuristic algorithms. It entails only embryonic mathematical functions, and it significantly avoids local optima.

In this paper, PSO algorithm is used in the OoO execution for task assignment problem in Ht-MPSoC. The major influences are given below.

- 1) The application of a PSO algorithm at the task level. In this step, detailed tasks are expressed as delegations for functional blocks in MPSoC systems like IP cores and processors.
- 2) The task systems with assorted dependences are considered to evaluate the performance of the proposed method and Joint Photographic Experts Group (JPEG) encoding is employed to optimize a real-time application.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 illustrates the related work performed on task assignment in Ht-MPSoC. In section 3, design modules are described. OoO execution is given in section 4. The PSO task assignment algorithm is given in section 5.

2. RELATED WORKS

Due to the wide-range of applications of MPSoC systems, parallelism transfers from the instruction stage to the task level. One way is to apply a reconfigurable FPGA system and assimilate acceleration engines like Chimaera [5], Garp [6], and OneChip [7]. In recent times, MPSoC scheduling has extended more consideration. In paper [8], Carvalho and Moraes studied the function of mapping processes in Network-on-Chip-based Ht-MPSoCs. In paper [9], the authors discover the reimbursements of thermally responsive task scheduling for MPSoCs.

In paper [10], Grewe and O'Boyle presented a static partitioning method using OpenCL. The method employs machine learning process. However, dynamic scheduling systems could gain scheduling, tuning methods at run time. In [11], Wang et al. presented an automatic parallel approach with MP-Tomasulo algorithm. Luk *et al.* [12] show a dynamic mapping process binding action to assorted processing cores together with GPU computing resources. Tactlessly, these studies did not take intertask necessities that regulate the task-level parallelization. Damos and Yalamanchili [13] explained about the task OoO execution. However, it did not explain about implementation pattern. Etsion *et al.* [14] presented an idea of OoO superscalar pipelines by considering the processors as

functional blocks. Berekovic and Niggemeier [15] presented an improved variety of the Tomasulo process with DSP based processor machines to realize OoO execution. Deng et al [16] proposed a hybrid processing module with an on-chip reconfigurable design on an FPGA to reinforce runtime monitoring and bookkeeping methods. Jenis et al. [17] studied the OoO implementation at the source code and compilation level. These studies cause unsatisfactory flexibility in several designs.

In paper [18], a Dynamic Adaptive Particle Swarm Optimization algorithm (DAPSO) was proposed to improve the operation of the conventional PSO algorithm to enhance the task runtime by mitigating the make time of a certain group of actions and increasing resource utilization. Also, task scheduling process was presented to program the detached action in the Cloud Computing. The authors combined the Dynamic PSO (DAPSO) algorithm with the Cuckoo search (CS) algorithm. The performance of the proposed algorithm was compared with that of the conventional PSO. In [19], the PSO algorithm is executed for the task assignment problem. The performance of the algorithm is compared with the genetic algorithm (population-based probabilistic heuristic) along the haphazardly generated task interaction graphs.

3. DESIGN MODEULES

3.1. Heterogeneous MPSoC

The schematic diagram of the MPSoC is depicted in figure 1. The MPSoC contains an ARM11MP Core Processor with four ARM1176 cores and a 512 KByte L2 memory. Processing elements (PEs) are created by eight ARM926 cores and two ARM1176 cores. Each processing element has its individual 64 KByte local memories. These PEs can be able to access their local cache. Hence, the provision for random access to the main memory is not available. The four Direct Memory Access Controllers (DMAC) are exploited for data transfer between global memories like RAM, scratch pad and local memories. Each PE has a distinct address location. The Core Manager is the central scheduling and apportionment unit. It is accountable for task data dependency monitoring, task scheduling, PE allocation and data allocation administration. In order to instantaneously establish links between different slave and master ports, an AXI 64-bit ARM PL301 interconnection is attached in the architecture. The interconnections in the units are shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: System model [2]

Figure 2: Task model [2]

The main object of the programming system is a task. A task is a group of instructions. Input and output data points are indicated at the initial time of an action. Figure 2 shows the task model with n inputs and m outputs. Data necessities between tasks are investigated at runtime.

To make the task programming system easier, a group of sovereign actions can be initialized by using the taskSet command. The number of tasks can be indicated at runtime. For every input and output measure, an offset can be denoted. It moves the pointer as per the iteration count of the action. If the offset is ignored the similar data are transmitted to the PE. Data inhabits in the local memory of a PE awaiting all actions of the taskSet are completed.

3.2. PROGRAMMING MODEL

Tasks denote the abstracted dynamic objects formed when application programming interfaces are treated by user applications. Additionally, tasks are considered as the functional abstract instructions, and each IP core is manipulated as a steadfast functional block to operate a particular hardware action. For each type of actions, the programmer must denote the direction of the factors clearly (input, output or input/output), to permit the programming unit to identify the intertask data dependences. The input and output is taken as a single data or stream array data, because of the execution of the hardware IP cores. Owing to the constraint of input/output buffer, data threats may occur. Input and output variables are represented in a declaration part. The dimension of the input and output arrays are indicated in the definition part.

All the Hardware Description Language (HDL) files must be premeditated in the user descriptions and restrictions. As soon as the Register-Transfer Level (RTL) codes are created, they are synthesized to netlists. Then they are placed and routed to bitstream instances.

4. OUT-OF-ORDER EXECUTION

The main function begins in the scheduling process. During the commencement of the program, each functional block is modified by storing the application binary into its reserved cache. In the meantime, each IP core is modified with the copied hardware bitstreams. These computing processors and IP cores remain in an inoperative state when the main program begins for procreating. Whenever the main program streams into an action that can be procreated to a computing processor or IP core, the protocol observes obligations with formerly delivered actions. Additionally, the scheduling processor is responsible of the action mapping phase that represents the action to a particular functional block, which is accomplished by a Xilinx Fast Simplex Link (FSL). When actions complete, the outcomes are reimbursed by means of the FSL bus. Consequently, the scheduling processor is disrupted. Provision for the interrupts is instigated using an interrupt controller that identifies the interrupt events for all the FSLs. It is significant to bring out all the apparent actions. These actions are fundamentally sequential functions with the help of the stipulated application program interface that specifies which segment of the code will be executed in the functional entities.

The description of dataflow execution unit is widened to a common heterogeneous multicore computing setup. Dataflow technologies manage dependences with gestures to signal generation and data availability. The data prerequisite will happen in the subsequent circumstances.

- 1) WAW Hazard: Some actions endeavor to obtain the write token of an instance whose write token is sustained by another action.
- 2) WAR Hazard: Some actions endeavor to obtain the write token of an instance whose read tokens are sustained by some other actions.
- 3) RAW Hazard: Some actions endeavor to obtain the read token of an instance whose write token is sustained by another action.

Figure 3: OoO execution model

Figure 3 depicts the OoO execution model which consists of two general-purpose processors (P_1 and P_2). The actions are extricated as OP: {write set}, {read set} pattern. As designated, OP represents the operand of various actions and the write/read set comprises the instances whose write/read token(s) should be acquired by tasks before execution. In figure 3, the objects are denoted as letters (e.g., a, b and c).

Generally, the function is divided into two steps:

1. The task dependence graph is attained by examining the dependence between actions. It is depicted in figure 2b. T_1 receives a write token of object c, and it consists of an intertask data dependence with T_2 . T_2 demands read token of

objectc. Correspondingly, T_2 contains a data dependence with T_5 on objectd, and T_3 contains a data dependence with T_5 on object f.

- The second step is representing the tasks on to a hardware module inconsistent with the task dependence graph. Fig. 2c exhibits the implementation of the code for the task execution unit on dual processors. The dotted lines show the interface between processors. The implementation begins with task T_1 . The tasks try to get a read token of objecta/and a write token of objectc. When it becomes positive, T_1 is suggested for accomplishment on an accessible core (P_1). Provisionally, when tasks try to get a write token of objecteand a read token of objectf and get succeeded, T_3 is suggested to execute on core P_2 . The T_1 implementation transfers to T_2 , which is abandoned because a read token of object c cannot be obtained due to the implementation of T_1 and the write tokens of object c. When the implementation of T_1 is over, it will discharge the write token of object c, which implies T_2 now can be ensured a read token of object c. Therefore, T_2 can be implemented when all its read tokens are available.

In Ht-MPSoCs, task-level parallelism must be enhanced dominously. To discuss this issue, OoO implementation can be employed. There are many issues related to Ht-MPSoC, like the identification of data dependences and the mapping of actions. Conversely, the task scheduling is more intricate in Ht-MPSoC. Figure 4 represents the OoO implementation on Ht-MPSoCs with two processors (P_1 and P_2). P_1 can perform actions T_x and P_2 can perform actions G_x .

Figure 4: OoO execution on heterogeneous MPSoCs

Besides, structural dependences must be considered along with the dataflow dependences. The threats between dynamic instances of the similar tasks is not observable at run time, e.g., dynamic illustrations of the tasks T_x , T_1 , and T_2 can be distributed at the same period only when there are satisfactory processors.

5. PARTICLE SWARM OPTIMIZATION AND TASK-LEVEL PARALLELISM -ALGORITHM

The goal of the task assignment process is to guarantee that every processing means is disseminated competently and equitably and hence resource functionality is enhanced. Numerous meta-heuristic protocols were presented for the dynamic task assignment process. In contrast, Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) is used since it is easy and effective in numerous applications. Some of the applications that have used PSO to solve hard problems like Scheduling problem, and the task allocation problem.

The PSO algorithm must improve the inertia weight since large amount of inertia weight enables a global search, however lesser inertia weight enables a local peak of the high dimensional function optimization task to enhance its global optimal and affinity speed.

Algorithm 1: PSO algorithm

- 1: Initialize particle dimension as similar to the dimension of ready actions in $\{t_{ij}\} \in T$.
- 2: Initialize particles location erratically from $PC = I, \dots, j$ and velocity v_i erratically.
- 3: For each particle, compute its fitness value $Cost(M) = \max(C_{total}(M)_j)$
- 4: If the fitness amount is superior than the previous best p_{best} , fix the present fitness amount as the latest p_{best} .
- 5: Choose the best particle as g_{best} .
- 6: For all particles, compute velocity using

$$v_i^{k+1} = \omega v_i^k + c_1 rand_1 \times (p_{best_i} - x_i^k) + c_2 rand_2 \times (g_{best_i} - x_i^k)$$

and update their positions using

$$x_i^{k+1} = x_i^k + v_i^{k+1}$$

v_i^{k+1} - velocity of particle i at iteration k

v_i^k - velocity of particle i at iteration $k+1$

ω - inertia weight

c_j - acceleration coefficients, $j=1,2$

$rand_i$ - random number between 0 and 1; $i=1,2$

$$Cost(M) = \max(C_{total}(M)_j) \quad \forall j \in P \quad (4)$$

The particle swarm optimization algorithm follows the below given principles.

- i. Proximity principle
- ii. Quality principle
- iii. Diverse principle
- iv. Principle of stability
- v. Stability principle

The population reverts to the quality measures P_{best} and g_{best} guarantee a multiplicity of response. The population alters its condition only when g_{best} modifies, this follows the principle of stability. The population alters when g_{best} gets modified.

6. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In the proposed design, there are two types of Microblaze processors, a scheduling Microblaze processor and several computing Microblaze processors. In dynamic operation, the scheduling Microblaze processor is employed to run-time PSO execution while TDA is operating on it during static operation. The scheduling processor and computing processors are attached with the sets of Xilinx FSL networks. The input and output are sent through the FSL bus networks. The accelerators of the proposed design are IP cores realized in Very-high-speed integrated circuit Hardware Description Language (VHDL) and allied with an amalgamated Xilinx FSL master and slave. The IP cores are constituted with adapted execution potentials in hardware to appraise the effect of their accomplishment time, and the IP cores are created as partial bitstream for altering the platform without difficulty. As the computing processors do, IP cores also accept inputs and send outputs through FSL bus networks. In this work, the modules of the Embedded Microprocessor Benchmark Consortium (EEMBC) benchmark test cases are employed for demonstration including IDCT, AES (encryption and decryption), DES (encryption and decryption), and JPEG. Figures 5-9 depict the waveforms of output signals of various modules like computing processor, scheduling processor, memory PC, Interrupt controller, Timer architecture.

Figure 5: Waveforms of clock, reset, input and output signals of memory PC module

Figure 6: Waveforms of clock, reset, input and output signals of Interrupt controller

Figure 7: Waveforms of clock, reset, input and output signals of Timer architecture

Figure 8: Waveforms of clock, reset, input and output signals of Computing processor

Figure 9: Waveforms of clock, reset, input and output signals of Scheduling Processor

The area utilization of various units in the existing design based on the scoreboarding process is compared with the proposed PSO based work and the results are illustrated in the tables given below. Tables 1-4 depict the area utilization of the existing work [1] and table 5 depicts the area utilization of the proposed work.

Table 1: Slice logic utilization of the existing work

Slice logic utilization	Used	Available	Utilization
Number of slice registers	2409	93120	2%
Number of slice LUTs	2747	46560	5%
Number used as Logic	2731	46560	5%
Number used as memory	16	16720	0%
Number used as RAM	16		

Table 2: Slice logic distribution of the existing work

Slice logic distribution	Used	Available	Utilization
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Number of LUT Flip flop pairs used	3942	-	-
Number with an unused Flip flop	1533	3942	38%
Number with an unused LUT	1195	3942	30%
Number of fully used LUT –FF pairs	1214	3942	30%
Number of unique control sets	469	-	-

Table 3: IO utilization of the existing work

IO utilization	Used	Available	Utilization
Number of IOs	257	-	-
Number of bonded IOBs	235	240	97%
IOB Flip flops / Latches	35	-	

Table 4: Utilization of specific features in the existing work

Specific feature utilization	Used	Available	Utilization
Number of Block RAM/FIFO	6	156	3%
Number of bonded IOBs	6	-	-
IOB Flip flops / Latches	5	32	15%

Table 5: Device utilization in the proposed work

Device utilization (estimated values)			
Logic utilization	Used	Available	Utilization
Number of slice registers	497	93120	0%
Number of slice LUTs	669	46560	1%
Number of fully used LUT –FF pairs	385	781	49%
Number of bonded IOBs	287	240	119%
Number of BUFG/BUFGCTRLS	3	32	9%

Table 6: Comparison of various parameters of existing and proposed work

Methodology	Area (buffers)	Speed	Powerconsumption(IOs)
Existingwork [1]	12%	1.63 ns	97.9
Proposed work	9%	0.73 ns	87.5

7. CONCLUSION

In the computing processors, the parallelization of tasks in processors is an imperative job for utilizing the sources effectively. In this paper, PSO algorithm is utilized for the task parallelization problem for heterogeneous MPSoC processors. The performance of the proposed PSO algorithm is computed experimentally and compared with the results of the conventional work. It is observed that the execution time for PSO algorithm is less. The dynamic operation examines the intertask dependences at run time. This paper proved that the PSO based OoO execution yields better results.

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